

RAILWAY SLEEPERS AND FAULTS OF STRESSED CONCRETE SLEEPERS

Mirzaxidova Ozoda Mirabdullayevna

Assistant, Tashkent State Transport University,

Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent

E-mail: ozoda_27@mail.ru

Fayziyev Sanjar Raxmatullayevich

Student, Tashkent State Transport University,

Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent

E-mail: n1ggablyck@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: Railways form the backbone of the economy of all countries, transporting both goods and passengers. Sleepers play a key role in ensuring track performance and safety in rail transport. This article briefly reviews the materials that were used to make sleepers in the early stages of railway development and the main faults in prestressed concrete sleepers. Extensive research has been carried out around the world on the static, dynamic and impact analysis of prestressed sleepers. It has been shown that most sleepers do not live up to their expected design life, resulting in huge replacement and repair costs.

Keywords: railway rail, sleepers, material, stressed concrete sleepers, reinforced concrete sleepers, wheel load malfunctions.

Materials used for sleepers

Timber: Wooden sleepers have been used on railroads for a long time, and they are reliable and efficient. The most significant advantage of using wooden sleepers is that they can be adapted to most railroad tracks. This advantage is due to the ease of handling wooden sleepers compared to other rigid sleepers. Problems that arise at the construction site can be solved in-house without the need for outside specialists.

Wooden sleepers are easily subject to mechanical wear and natural rotting, which leads to their destruction. Wooden sleepers are predominantly damaged by fungus and rot. Termite attack also damages a significant number of sleepers. Because railroad ties withstand large amounts of transverse shear loads, the logs splinter at the ends, rendering them useless. The use of wood also results in deforestation, so the environmental impact is very high. In addition, the use of chemically impregnated wood poses a disposal risk. These negative effects have led to the use of other materials.

2. Cast iron. Cast iron sleepers have a lifespan of five to six decades. They can be overmolded and have a significantly high scrap value. In addition to providing considerable support area, they are stronger at the rail junction.

Despite these advantages, as with most cast iron elements, they corrode more quickly, so they are not recommended for use in coastal areas. Cast-iron sleepers are damaged during derailment and therefore have a high replacement cost. In addition to the need for a large number of fasteners, they also cannot absorb shocks. Added to this is the high initial cost, so cast iron sleepers are not economically feasible.

3. Steel sleepers. Steel sleepers last on railroads for decades. Unlike wooden sleepers, steel sleepers are not subject to rot and are not affected by vermin. The use of steel sleepers provides the best and easiest connection between rail and sleeper. In addition to providing superior lateral stiffness, steel sleepers also have a high scrap value. Because of their higher quality compared to cast iron sleepers, they do not require extra attention after laying. Their resistance to creep also gives them an added advantage. Because of the factors mentioned above, they are suitable for high speeds and high loads compared to cast iron sleepers.

4. Concrete sleepers. With an expected lifespan of about half a century, concrete sleepers are the most durable of all the above sleepers. Because of their heavy weight, they can provide exceptional lateral track stability. In addition to their resistance

to corrosion compared to other materials, concrete sleepers demonstrate high performance against creep. Their ability to resist termite attack and their suitability for use on almost all types of soil make them widely used. Although the initial cost of producing these sleepers is high, their payback in half a century of service more than makes up for the high cost.

The rigid nature of concrete sleepers makes them difficult to handle. Their inability to be adapted to different operating conditions compared to wooden sleepers poses some problems. Compared to wooden sleepers, concrete sleepers are rigid. Conventional concrete sleepers have shown their inability to withstand the cyclic nature of the loads acting on them during their service life.

The main faults in prestressed concrete sleepers are

1. Deterioration of the rail saddle. In modern prestressed concrete sleepers, rail saddle failure is the most common occurrence. There are many reasons why rail saddle deterioration occurs, and among them, abrasion of the saddle is the most likely cause of rail saddle deterioration [1]. Relative motion between the pads and the surface of the concrete rail saddle causes wear of the concrete from the surface. The load from the wheels is transferred to the pads, which in turn transfer it to the rail. These loads are then taken up by the sleepers. During this process, a shear force acts at the boundary between the rail and the pad. When this force exceeds the static friction at the interface, sliding occurs; the concrete absorbs the transferred deformation. When this deformation in the concrete crosses the fatigue limit, it leads to deterioration and eventually, after significant cycles of loading, the concrete particles detach from the rail seating area [2]. Fig.3 shows the scheme of rail saddle wear.

Fig.3 Diagram of rail saddle deterioration

2.Center-bound damage and longitudinal cracks. Due to the ever-increasing demand for improved rail transport efficiency, high-strength railroad ties are an urgent necessity. Sleepers fracture in tension, experiencing high magnitude and high-frequency loads that occur during train traffic. The origin of the cracks has been traced to the location of the rawhide plug, with tensile stresses resulting from prestressing forces in the same area being the primary cause of their development. These stresses will eventually lead to the development of longitudinal cracks due to increased tensile stress around this area[4]. Figure 4 shows the development of tensile cracks in the center of the sleepers.

Fig.4 Tensile cracks in the center of sleepers

Literature:

1. Kernes R G, Shurpali A A, Edwards J R, Dersch M S, Lange D A и Barkan C P 2014 Исследование механики износа рельсовых седел и методов повышения износостойкости рельсовых седел из бетонных шпал Proceedings of Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part F: Journal of Rail and Rapid Transit 228(6) 581-9.
2. Kernes R G, Edwards J R, Dersch M S, Lange D A и Barkan C P 2011 Исследование динамических фрикционных свойств бетонного рельсового седла и накладки на перемычку и их влияние на износ рельсового седла
3. Greve M J, Dersch M S, Edwards J R, Barkan C P, Mediavilla J и Wilson B 2016 Влияние проникновения частиц на распределение нагрузки на сиденья рельсов на тяжелых грузовых железных дорогах. Международный журнал железнодорожного транспорта 4(2) 98-112.
4. Rezaie F, Shiri M R и Farnam S M 2012 Экспериментальные и численные

исследования контроля продольных трещин в предварительно напряженных бетонных шпалах. *Engineering Failure Analysis* 26 21-30.

5. Ременников А.М. и Каевунруен С. Экспериментальная оценка нагрузки состаренных железнодорожных бетонных шпал. *Engineering Structures*. 2014 Oct 1; 76:147-62.

6. Kodirov Nodirbek, Mirzahidova Ozoda FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF TRACK STRUCTURE // *Universum: технические науки*. 2022. №9-5 (102). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/finite-element-analysis-of-track-structure> (дата обращения: 20.12.2022).

7. Mirabdullayevna M. O. Diagnostics of the Roadbed // *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*. – 2020. – С. 41-43

8. Mirzakhidova Ozoda Mirabdullayevna, & Azizova Sarvinoz Ilhomjon qizi. (2022). PRINCIPLES FOR MODELLING THE SPATIAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF FLOW CONSTRUCTION PROCESSES. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(1), 239–244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/51>

9. Mirzakhidova O. M. PROSPECTS FOR THE CONSTRUCTION OF RAILWAYS IN UZBEKISTAN // *Academic research in educational sciences*. – 2021.–Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 1134-1138.

10. Begaliyevich, Abdualiev Elyorbek, Mirzahidova Ozoda Mirzabdulayebna, and Khamidov Mahsud Kamolovich. "STUDIES OF THE MODE OF OPERATION OF CULVERTS ON RAILWAY LINES." *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI* (2022): 307-310.

11. BEGALIYEVICH A. E., MIRZABDULAYEBNA M. O., KAMOLOVICH K. M. TO EXAMINE THE IMPACT OF THE FORCES FALLING FROM THE STRUCTURE OF THE MOVEMENT ON THE WATERPROOFING PIPES IN HIGH-SPEED AND HIGH-SPEED RAILWAYS // *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*. – 2022.–С.1-4.

12.Музаффарова М.К., Мирзахидова О.М., Махомаджанов Ш.Ш.
МОНИТОРИНГ ШПАЛ ТИПА ВF70 НА УЧАСТКАХ АО «УЗБЕКИСТАН
ТЕМИР ЙУЛЛАРИ» // Universum: технические науки : электрон. научн. журн.
2022. 12(105). URL: <https://7universum.com/ru/tech/archive/item/14790> (дата
обращения: 27.12.2022).